

Supplementary Material D

Extended Discussion

D1. Internal and External Validity of Included Studies (Study DIAD; Valentine & Cooper, 2008)

(Extension to section 4.3: Methodological Comparison to Thielsch, Scharfen et al. (2019) & Limitations)

Despite the refined inclusion criteria, the overall quality of the included studies was mediocre, as assessed by the Study Design and Implementation Assessment Device (Study DIAD; Valentine & Cooper, 2008). Internal validity was acceptable across all studies, ensuring a causal relationship between interface aesthetics and user performance. This was supported by the refined inclusion criteria, particularly the requirement for significant aesthetic manipulations, and the analysis of confounding variables as a moderator. In contrast, the studies received low ratings for external validity. This was partly because the Study DIAD question in this category was not fully applicable to all included primary studies. For instance, in the case of context-specific interfaces (e.g., vehicle navigation systems), it was considered acceptable for studies to focus on a single context provided they included diverse user groups. In contrast, universally used interfaces (e.g., search engines, corporate websites) required evaluation across different settings and user groups. Regardless of interface type, assessing multiple outcome measures is essential to enhancing external validity, yet this was rarely done.

(For a discussion on construct and statistical validity, see the main text.)

D2. Recommendations for Future Systematic Reviews

(Extension to section 4.4: Recommendations for Future Research)

A fundamental challenge in systematic reviews lies in developing a comprehensive and replicable search strategy for bibliographic databases. Each database imposes unique requirements for constructing search terms, including differences in syntax, field codes, and conjunction logic. In this meta-analysis, even logically identical search terms produced varying results across databases, introducing uncertainty and potential errors. To address this, we maintained a consistent approach to search term development (see Supplement A, section A2). For instance, wildcards and truncation symbols, which function differently across platforms, were avoided in favor of explicitly including variations in word spellings, such as American and British English. To ensure replicability, systematic reviews should clearly document not only the search terms used but also any database-specific adjustments made.

Tools like the Polyglot Search Translator (Clark et al., 2020) can facilitate the translation of search strings across platforms but was not used here, as the databases searched (e.g., ACM Digital Library, ProQuest Dissertations & Theses) extended beyond those supported by the tool. Furthermore, it is important that the search strategy is validated by comparing the database search results against a set of representative articles. This aligns with PRISMA 2020 guidelines, which emphasize transparency in search processes (cf. Page et al., 2021).

Managing large datasets remains a significant obstacle, as most literature management tools are not designed to handle large volumes of records (e.g., 40,000), resulting in slow performance. For this meta-analysis, we used Rayyan (Ouzzani et al., 2016) for study selection due to its free availability, ability to manage large datasets, and the option to retain duplicates for manual review (unlike tools such as Mendeley Desktop, which removes exact duplicates automatically; American University of Beirut, 2023). However, multiple tools were used for different review steps—SRA Deduplicator for deduplication (Forbes et al., 2024), Rayyan (Ouzzani et al., 2016) and RS (Chai et al., 2021) for title and abstract screening, and SRA SpiderCite (Clark et al., 2020) for citation searches—requiring frequent transitions between programs and data conversion between formats (e.g., RIS, CSV, EndNote XML, XLSX). This increases the risk of data loss and results in a reduction of overall efficiency. To address these challenges, tool developers and researchers should prioritize integrating tools for seamless data handling and developing guidelines for combining software solutions for systematic reviews, such as those proposed by Clark et al. (2020) for SRA tools. Expanding access to free tools like Rayyan or SRA would further improve efficiency and accessibility for researchers.

Using a semiautomated screening process with machine learning proved to be a valuable time-saver in this meta-analysis. RS reduced the manual screening workload by approximately 93%, leaving only 1,500 records for manual review, which allowed more time for tasks like full-text screening, citation searches, and coding. However, selecting (semi)automated tools requires careful consideration, as the tool's algorithm must align with the specific requirements of the research field. For RS, this was addressed by training the algorithm with a set of seed articles that represented the defined inclusion criteria (Chai et al., 2021). While (semi)automated screening, of course, carries the risk of excluding relevant studies, such risks are not exclusive to automation; manual screening can similarly suffer from human screening error (Bannach-Brown et al., 2019). Given that systematic reviews are time- and resource-intensive, future research should focus on refining and validating

(semi)automated screening processes to accelerate the sharing of research findings (Clark et al., 2020).

Assessing the quality and risk of bias in the included primary studies is a critical step in systematic reviews. In this meta-analysis, we used the Study DIAD by Valentine & Cooper (2008) because it can be customized to various research contexts by answering contextual questions that define the aspects later rated in the design and implementation questions (see Supplement B, section B2). Still, some questions required refinement during coding, such as distinguishing between in-person and online studies or context-specific versus widely used interfaces. Given the weak replicability of studies in the HCI research field, the Study DIAD's binary response scale was not precise enough to capture the variability in these studies. Except for these limitations, the Study DIAD proved effective for assessing study quality in the HCI context. In line with PRISMA guidelines (Page et al., 2021), researchers should prioritize a systematic and quantifiable approach to assess study quality, enhancing review reliability and enabling comparisons across research fields.

(For recommendations and guidelines for future primary studies in HCI, see the main text.)